

Edible Insects and their products for nutritional and medicinal value within the Tiwa and Karbi Community in Langsomepi Development Block, Assam

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Insects are the most diverse group of organisms in the phylum Arthropoda, let alone the entire world. They contain high amounts of proteins and other nutritious compounds. Entomophagy is the practice of consumption of insects and their products for nutritional purposes. Also known as Insectivory, this has been practiced since ancient times and hence is rich in culture and traditions. Knowledge of consumption of insects has been passed from generations through the word of mouth, some being for nutritional purposes and some consumed to cure certain diseases. Insects provides as food for many ethnic groups of North-east India. For Tiwa and Karbi people of Langsomepi development block of Karbi Anglong district, insects have been an important dietary supplement and also an integral component of their socio-cultural life. A total of 19 species of insects were documented in this study that are preferentially consumed by those Tiwa and Karbi population. Most of these species belong to the orders Orthoptera and Lepidoptera. Their medicinal properties have been very prominent and effective but this traditional knowledge is disintegrating due to modernization . Also, availability of these insects have reduced overtime due to various factors. So it's an urgent need to document these practices should be further studied to evaluate them for the benefit of humankind.

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